

Fast re-OBJ: Real-time object re-identification in rigid scenes

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Abstract Re-identifying objects in a rigid scene across varying viewpoints (object Re-ID) is a challenging task, in particular when there are similar, even identical objects coexist in the same environment. Discriminative features play no doubt an essential role in addressing this challenge, while for practical deployment, real-time performance is another desired attribute. We therefore propose a novel framework, named **Fast re-OBJ**, that is able to improve both Re-ID accuracy and processing speed via tight coupling between the instance segmentation module and embedding generation module. The rich object encoding in the instance segmentation backbone is directly shared to the embedding generation module for training a more discriminative representation via a triplet network. Moreover, we create datasets with the segmentation outputs using real-time object detectors to train and evaluate our object embedding module. With extensive experiments, we prove that our proposed **Fast re-OBJ** improves the object Re-ID accuracy by 5% and the speed is 5× faster compared to the state-of-the-art methods. The code and dataset will be publicly available upon the paper acceptance.

Keywords Object Re-identification · Embedding · Triplet Network · Real-time · Ranking

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1 Introduction

The capability of assigning the unique identity to each object detected in a video stream plays an important role in many vision-based tasks, such as object tracking or 3D object localisation [32]. Given a detection/segmentation of an object, i.e. a probe/anchor (A) (we use probe and A interchangeably), the task of object re-identification (Re-ID) is to match the probe correctly against a set of images containing known objects (i.e. gallery). Throughout the literature review, person Re-ID [49, 6, 45] has been a very active research topic for at least a couple of decades. However, the study that focuses on object Re-ID remains much less explored. While object re-ID plays a fundamental role in most of object-centered SLAM systems for anchoring 3D static objects with semantic understanding in both indoor and outdoor scenes [33, 25, 26, 12]. Most works simply bypass the object tracking, i.e. data-association across multiple views in both short-term and long-term, by using detections with either ground-truth association or a short tracklet estimated by out-of-the-box trackers, and focus mainly on the object shape abstraction [33, 25] or 6D pose estimation [26, 12].

We aim to address object Re-ID so that it could benefit a more robust object-based SLAM system in challenging scenarios with scene clutters, appearance similarity, and large changes in viewpoints. Compared to person Re-ID, object Re-ID exposes new challenges since objects in close proximity can also be identical, e.g. chairs of the same model coexist in a meeting room, while it is a rather rare case when multiple visually identical people coexist. When objects with very similar, or even the same appearance coexist in the scene, using only foreground (fg) images, cannot be sufficient, as the object visual features like texture, material, and shape

are no longer distinguishable attributes. To address this challenge, re-OBJ [2], one of the pioneer works on object Re-ID, exploits the rigid scene and complements the visual cues with the background (bg) by proposing a combined deep feature from both the fg and bg to train a triplet network for the task of object Re-ID. Re-OBJ strengthens the feature distinguishing power, however, it is not designed with real-time processing in mind, with a running speed less than 4 Hz on a standard PC. This would comprise the real-time performance of an object tracking system as the recent object detector [9] and tracking modules [7] can both achieve more than 30 Hz at run time. This shortcoming can be a clear and decisive drawback for an online tracking system running on e.g. a robotic platform.

We therefore propose **Fast re-OBJ** to address real-time object Re-ID in cluttered rigid indoor scenes. **Fast re-OBJ** proposes a framework that is comprised of embedding generation module (EGM) which is tightly coupled with the object detection module, and a triplet-based matching (TbM) module. **EGM module includes resized, bounding-box (bbx) projected, and b-fg separated feature maps peculiar to instance segmentation backbone (ISB)**. To obtain the method efficiency, we exploit a real-time ISB, YOLACT++ [9], and further propose a novel procedure for embedding generation by reusing the rich object-related encoding in the ISB that is pre-trained on large-scale dataset. This differs us from re-OBJ [2] which applies additional ResNets and related elements to extract features from the masked outputs obtained by Mask R-CNN [15]. Our proposed embedding generation module directly exploits the intermediate outputs of the ISB to generate feature embeddings for triplet-based training, hence avoiding repeated feature extraction during ISB and EG. Our main contributions can be summarised as follows:

- (1) We propose a real-time object Re-ID framework **Fast re-OBJ** that improves both the Re-ID accuracy and processing speed compared to the state-of-the-art methods.
- (2) We propose a novel EGM that enables the direct knowledge sharing with the ISB, and then produces more discriminative representations **passing through a fully-connected (FC) layer with fine-tuned weights** via the TbM module. **Our framework can eventually exploit the final embedding within the TbM module directly to distinguish the queries from dissimilar objects without requiring any fine-tuning or transfer learning process and hence achieves discriminative features.**
- (3) We provide novel datasets to facilitate the training and evaluation of object Re-ID methods. The datasets are built with real-scene capturing, and

the fg/bg segmentation is achieved by both ground-truth annotations and the state-of-the-art real-time instance segmentation method.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 discusses the related works on object detection, image retrieval and object Re-ID. Section 3 describes the our proposed framework with a detailed description for each module. Section 4 provides the ablation studies and baseline comparisons with the real scene datasets. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper providing perspectives for future work.

2 Related Work

We mainly cover the literature on *object detection and instance segmentation*, *image retrieval*, and *person and object Re-ID*, which are closely related to our work.

Object detection and instance segmentation: For object detection/segmentation, the main steps can be summarised as: i) feature extraction with a pre-trained network, ii) region proposal using the extracted features, and iii) prediction heads that are composed of FC layers classifying proposals of each region. Detection/segmentation models frequently exploit models such as AlexNet [18], VGGNet [35], Inception [36], ResNet [14] or their variants [44], which are originally used for object recognition, to extract features crucial for their prediction heads. For example YoloV3 [29] uses a modified ResNet while previous versions are using AlexNet and modified VGGNet, respectively. Mask R-CNN, an instance segmentation model, is built on top of Faster R-CNN [30] where ResNet is the backbone model and it also has a mask segmentation part. YOLACT++ [9] is a recent real-time instance segmentation method, which achieves real-time performance by performing in parallel prototype mask generation and mask coefficient prediction for each instance before linearly combining these two outputs to produce the instance masks.

Image retrieval: Given a probe containing an object of interest, the image retrieval task aims to search for images containing similar instances from a gallery (a large database of images) with a possibility of fusing extra information channels [13, 28, 31, 40, 24]. The study by [13] proposes an image retrieval method using fixed-length region features generated by a fine-tuned network that is particularly focused on the landmark site images. Likewise, GEM, introduced by [28], also uses a fine-tuned network for image retrieval and exploits structure from motion to select training data in an unsupervised aspect with the goal of increasing

variation. GEM(AP) by [31] is built on top of GEM, claims a better accuracy by training the network according to the list-wise ranking loss. In addition, [42] presents an unsupervised framework towards image retrieval applications that also localises target objects as activation maps. Moreover, [34] analyses the impacts of fine-tuning and provides basic spatial re-ranking results performed upon a feature proposal network. On the other hand, [38] asserts an improvement on the image retrieval task with a framework that employs regional aggregations as a result of deep features and object regions.

Person and Object Re-ID: Different from the image retrieval task, given a probe, Re-ID aims to find the images containing the exact same object/person captured from different viewpoints within the gallery images [2, 5, 45]. Image retrieval methods are likely to fail the Re-ID task when multiple instances of the same class coexist in the scene. Re-ID is commonly considered in the person/pedestrian domain, where the majority of studies are appearance-based [11] and follow main steps as: *i*) feature extraction and reforming to obtain useful embeddings from targets [1], and *ii*) metric-based ranking as a result of comparing queries with gallery images [27]. Furthermore, [11, 4] exploit symmetry of local features extracted by classical methods from background subtracted targets to compare with the gallery images employing Euclidean distance. On the other hand, [3] enriches the extracted foreground target person visual cues of histogram and epitome with temporal information, which matches features via minimum distance. The study in [39], namely PERMA-TRACK, is an extension of CenterTrack [48] and it leverages a spatio-temporal, recurrent memory module to enable establishing the tracking between the current frame content and all previous frames. The model called OSNet [47] considers both different spatial scales with a combination of multiple scales to produce omni-scale features for person re-id via a unified aggregation gate that is coupled with residual block. Besides, the work in [43] called AGRL asserts graph neural networks to facilitate the contextual connections between regional features via pose and feature affinity information. Readers are referred to the studies in [45, 46] for the most recent advances in person Re-ID.

For the task of object Re-ID in rigid scenes, [2] presents an approach, re-OBJ, to predict the exact same image with the probe based on the observations extracted by Mask-RCNN. Once re-OBJ acquires the bg/fg splits from its instance segmentation backbone, these are fed to ResNet yielding encodings by concatenating the outputs. Re-OBJ employs the joint represen-

tation of both bg and fg, to train a triplet network which first extracts spatial information and obtains the final embedding for the triplet loss layer. Moreover, object Re-ID has also been incorporated into a more complicated object tracking framework [37, 21, 20]. The study given by [19] targets object Re-ID for object segmentation purpose by subtracting the sequential frames. In addition, [37] proposes a Re-ID-based tracker that benefits from a learned matching function with an embedding trained on a comprehensive dataset which can be directly applied to unseen targets without adaptation. Furthermore, [21] and [20] introduce re-ranking based object Re-ID approaches towards object segmentation and tracking in videos.

Our work mainly focuses on the object Re-ID task without addressing a complete tracking framework. Although we exploit bg and fg splits and the use of a triplet-based ranking approach as in re-OBJ [2], we achieve a higher Re-ID accuracy at a faster speed by exploiting the fast instance segmentation backbone YOLACT++ for both detection and embedding generation which allows for knowledge sharing across modules.

3 Fast re-OBJ

In order to address the problem of object Re-ID in real-time, we propose a system that tightly combines the real-time object detector YOLACT++ with embedding generation and object matching (see Fig. 1). We avoid using the final segmentation output from the instance segmentation backbone followed by ResNet for feature extraction as in re-OBJ [2], as it requires additional processing for feature extraction which inevitably slows down the system. Instead, we directly exploit the rich instance knowledge that has been already encoded in the backbone of YOLACT++ via its feature pyramid network base, for embedding generation thanks to the image-sized prototype masks in particular by the ProtoNet branch with its fully convolutional network structure, thus enabling fast processing and knowledge sharing across modules. YOLACT++ enables us to produce enriched features as of prototype masks via its ProtoNet module that consists of k -masks corresponding to FC layers as a linear combination of them with the coefficients, namely semantic classes, bboxes, and instance masks, produced by the prediction head working simultaneously. We therefore exploit the features from EGM instantly to compare within TbM by projecting the bbox coordinates directly onto the ProtoNet outputs as refined features without requiring an extra training related process. We set the number of so called prototype masks, k , to be 32 as the original YOLACT++

Fig. 1 Object Re-ID aims to correctly associate the probe with gallery images containing the exact object. We carefully exploit the intermediate encoding of the object detection backbone, to benefit not only the processing speed, but also the discriminative power of the embedding trained via a triplet network. The triplet network aims to push A, i.e. the image at query, away from the Negatives (Ns), i.e. images without the object, while bringing A closer to the Positives (Ps), i.e. the images with the exact same input object.

suggests. The main advantage of YOLACT++ architecture is that it facilitates us exploiting prototype embedding that are already semantically rich.

To generate the embedding for each A, we map its bbx output on the averaged and resized ProtoNet output to segment the fg from the bg. Two features that correspond to fg and bg respectively are produced and concatenated to form the final embedding. For robust object matching using our proposed embedding, we employ a triplet-based module which requires an offline training of a discriminator that differentiate between an input A, P and N images with a triplet loss. Images as As contain the queried objects in the gallery, Ps contain the A objects from different views, and Ns contain other objects that are not As. Note that the same embedding generation procedure is applied to the Ps and Ns.

At test time, each segmented probe passes through the embedding generation followed by the triplet loss computation. We then apply re-ranking based on the Euclidean distance between the triplets to find the best match, i.e. the closest one between the A and P.

3.1 Instance segmentation backbone

We use YOLACT++ to split bg and fg images, for its real-time and accurate performance. YOLACT++ is built on top of the architecture of YOLACT [8], with a few modifications, e.g. an efficient mask rescore network and deformable convolutions for the alignment of feature sampling and instances, that further boosts the

detection accuracy while maintaining its advantageous speed.

The feature extraction stage of YOLACT++, which consists of ResNet-101 with feature pyramid network, is fast because it performs two paths in parallel. One of the paths makes use of the FC layers that are well-performing at producing semantic vectors, i.e. the “mask coefficients”, while the other path makes use of convolutional layers that are good at producing spatially coherent masks, i.e. the “prototype masks”. The prediction head of YOLACT++ is borrowed from RetinaNet [23], which is modified to have an extra mask coefficient branch and be shallower for instance segmentation mask generation and speed purposes, respectively. The approach is moreover enhanced thanks to quick and effective mask rescore network that reranks the mask predictions in accordance with the quality of the mask. By a new non-maximum suppression (NMS) technique, YOLACT++ improves the classical NMS, which eliminates the unnecessary region proposals of the prediction head outputs and hence implements them on the original input. On the other hand, YOLACT++ is a collection of non-local prototype masks across the whole image before predicting a set of linear combination coefficients for each instance. This real-time instance segmentation method crops with a projected bbx after linearly combining the prototypes with appropriately predicted bboxes. In essence, prediction head generates bboxes, class labels, and masks for each instance and ProtoNet produces feature map for the entire input image. The prediction head and ProtoNet structures of YOLACT++ run simultaneously, which enables us to project the bboxes

Fig. 2 The pipeline of the proposed embedding generation for As, Ps, and Ns. The features that are extracted from the entire input image pass through the ProtoNet and Prediction Head of YOLACT++ simultaneously following the feature pyramid network. Prototype outputs are first averaged from $138 \times 138 \times 32$ prototype masks corresponding to the complete input image to produce a feature map of 138×138 and then resized to the size of the original input, which is 550×550 for our pipeline depending on the base image size of YOLACT++ model employed to align the bboxes of each detected instance. The averaged later resized feature map of the whole input image is split into fg and bg, which are obtained based on the bboxes that the Prediction Head of YOLACT++ provides for every instance separately. The splits as of fg and bg are subsequently processed by particular FC layers to generate their corresponding 2048-d feature vectors. The final embedding is a 4096-d vector obtained as a result of concatenating the two vectors corresponding to fg and bg.

onto feature maps instead of drawing bboxes on the original input image. We thus exploit the enriched features of ProtoNet reliably to form final embeddings after splitting the feature map into fg and bg. In particular, there are 32 prototype masks in total which are generated by a custom architecture, which is composed of fully convolutional layers, *ProtoNet* (as shown in Fig. 2). The averaging process has taken place for each of the 32 feature maps generated by the ProtoNet to produce a one-single 138×138 output to be resized to the original input size and then be projected onto by the outputs of the other branch. For each instance that survives after the NMS, the final mask or bboxes for the instance is constructed by linearly combining the outputs of these two branches. Therefore, YOLACT++ empowers our **Fast re-OBJ** algorithm with prototype features from its deep backbone by producing robust masks, and higher resolution prototypes achieves both high-quality embeddings and satisfactory performance on smaller objects.

3.2 Embedding generation

In order to reuse the knowledge embeddings from the YOLACT++ backbone, we make use of the intermediate outputs from the ProtoNet architecture, knowing that they are rich in encoding spatial knowledge. As shown in Fig. 2, 32 prototype masks with the dimension of $138 \times 138 \times 1$ are first averaged in a pixel-wise

manner, resulting in a single-channel image. We then use the coordinates of the object bboxes to locate the corresponding part in the averaged ProtoNet output. As the size of bboxes is aligned to the input image with the width and height of 550, we therefore resize the averaged ProtoNet output to the size of $550 \times 550 \times 1$ to properly locate the bboxes on it.

Note that the use of bboxes, rather than the output mask, is an experimental choice as the bboxes provides a higher Re-ID accuracy at a faster speed (see details in Section 4.2). For the fg of ProtoNet image, we perform zero-padding for the area that is outside the bboxes, while for the bg of ProtoNet image, we perform zero-padding within the bboxes area. Both the fg and bg of ProtoNet images are then passed through an FC layer to extract fixed-sized features of 2048-d vectors, which are finally concatenated as the final embedding to be passed to the triplet network. In order to train with the feature embedding, we use the pre-trained weights of ProtoNet from YOLACT++, while only keeping the weights of the last layer of the ProtoNet and the later FC layers trainable (as shown in Fig. 2). Thus the last layer of ProtoNet and the FC layers are fine-tuned with the embedding training on our ScanNet dataset.

3.3 Triplet-based matching

A triplet-based ranking loss function aims to learn a metric indicating the distance between inputs by bring-

ing the P close to the A and pushing the N away from the A with a margin. Each probe image is compared against all gallery samples and scores are calculated between the probe and gallery images measuring distances in the embedding space. The scores are sorted and ranked where a rank is determined at which only a true match occurs.

We modify the ProtoNet fully convolutional network as a triplet architecture by the pairwise ranking to learn the image similarities via the triplet ranking loss. For a triplet of images I_{iA} , I_{iP} , and I_{iN} as being the A, P and N, respectively, we aim to learn an embedding function that minimises the distance between the A-P pair (vice versa for the A-N pair) as suggested in [41], such that:

$$D(I_{iA}, I_{iP}) < D(I_{iA}, I_{iN}),$$

where $D(\cdot)$ gives the squared Euclidean distance.

We can define the triplet ranking loss function as:

$$\mathcal{L}(I_{iA}, I_{iP}, I_{iN}) = \max[0, M + D(I_{iA}, I_{iP}) - D(I_{iA}, I_{iN})]$$

where M is the triplet margin regulating the pairwise distances.

During training, we prepare triplets with batch hard strategy [16], where the triplet loss is computed over a batch of embeddings with the pairwise distances between A, P, and N.

4 Experiments

In section 4.1, we first introduce the datasets for the training of **Fast re-OBJ** using both ground-truth annotations and ISB outputs. Section 4.2 performs an ablation study for our design choices with respect to the proposed embedding generation. Finally in section 4.3, we evaluate our proposed approach against the state-of-the-art methods for addressing object Re-ID and the closely related image retrieval task.

Regarding the performance measures, we follow the commonly used evaluation protocol for object Re-ID task with the accuracy for rank-N matches by a Cumulative Matching Characteristic (CMC) curve and the mean average precision (mAP). Note that we only account for the match to the *exact* instance as a correct match, and the matches to similar objects are regarded as wrong matches. In addition, the speed in terms of the number of processed frame per second (fps) and processing time per frame in terms of milliseconds (ms) are also reported to validate our claim about the real-time performance of the proposed method.

4.1 Dataset preparation

To train and evaluate the performance of our approach, we build our dataset based on ScanNet [10] which contains 1513 indoor RGBD scene scans including object annotations, 3D camera poses, and scene reconstructions. The scans of ScanNet are principally arranged for the tasks 3D object classification and detection, semantic voxel labeling, and CAD model retrieval. We selected 32 scenes from ScanNet for generating our datasets, which contains relatively more unique objects per sequence. Since ScanNet provides depth-color aligned raw point cloud (PCD) data with reconstructed meshes and relevant annotations, we acquire the information required for building a ground-truth dataset for re-id purpose using camera intrinsics and extrinsics, and IMU data for each mesh that all located at unique positions. A typical ScanNet folder consists of a mesh file including raw PCD, aggregation file including object id, segments id and label, segmentation file including segments id and vertex, and meta file including axis-aligned matrix. We primarily export each scan and filter out the semantic labels to get MS COCO-style [22] labels that the YOLACT++ is trained on. Then we segment each object out from 3D scene depending on the pose of the camera that captures the scene with semantic labels and instance IDs. We consequently have 2D images with bboxes, masks, classes, and IDs as the ground-truth data.

Our framework relies on concatenating the features of bg, fg, and full images, thereby our dataset folder contains subfolders for scenes that contain subfolders for IDs that contain 3 subfolders for triplets as A, P, and N and each of them contains 8 images. Fig. 3 illustrates the sample images representing the As, Ps and Ns, that form the triplet for a single instance, herein TV. We scrutinise the number of occurrence of objects throughout the whole sequence to select the images to form the triplet subfolders. If an instance has been seen more than 32 frames, then we account it for a valid object to form the triplet subfolder, where $2 \times 8 = 16$ images containing the object will be randomly selected to form the A and P subfolder, respectively. We then form the N subfolder by selecting 8 images of a different object that belongs to the same scene. As the different object in the same scene might correspond to the same class of the anchor object, this makes our triplet learning in a hard-negative mining manner.

To form embeddings using bg and fg, an instance segmentation technique is needed. However, even the most state-of-the-art instance segmentation methods, e.g. Mask R-CNN or YOLACT++, can lead to wrong labeling and/or incomplete masks as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 3 Sample images that comprise the As, Ps and Ns for a TV instance. As and Ps correspond to the same instance in a scene while the Negatives correspond to a different object within the same scene.

Fig. 4 Examples from the dataset are shown in the first column, followed by the foreground bboxes detected by YOLACT++ or Mask R-CNN in the second column and the corresponding background in the third column. The first row shows the ground-truth sample for a “chair” instance with its ground-truth foreground and background. The second and third rows indicate the correct foregrounds of the same “chair” instance at a different view point, detected by YOLACT++ and Mask R-CNN, respectively. While the last two rows show the wrong foreground that has been detected as a “chair” instance in a scene where no chair exists, by YOLACT++ and Mask R-CNN, respectively. This is to show that the instance segmentation methods may provide wrong class labelling.

The fg images in our datasets is illustrated in the middle column of Fig. 4. Moreover, we replace the region

inside the bboxes or masks with zeros, yielding the bg images as shown in the last column of Fig. 4. To investigate the impact of imperfect mask segmentation on the Re-ID performance, we prepared two sets of data, *ReOBJ-GT* and *ReOBJ-Y++* using ground-truth (GT) annotations and YOLACT++ detector, respectively. For *ReOBJ-GT*, we obtain the instance labels from the annotated 3D scene meshes. For each scene, we project the 3D points corresponding to each instance to the image plane with the provided camera pose and intrinsics, to acquire the unique instance ID and its GT bbox. Note that the IDs per object are scene-specific in ScanNet. For example ID ‘1’ can be a *chair* in one scene but a *TV* in another. There are also various number of unique instances at each scene, we consequently arrange the folders specific to instance IDs to contain 8 images per triplet. In *ReOBJ-GT*, we also exclude images if the objects are occluded by more than 15%, or if their projected bboxes are too small, or out of the image. In total, *ReOBJ-GT* contains 849 unique IDs and 66,869 images.

For *ReOBJ-Y++*, we run YOLACT++ as ISB on the frames we selected from ScanNet within the 32 scenes with a confidence score of 0.5. Considering that object IDs matter for our application rather than object classes, we stored the images according to the unique IDs as triplets per scene. From all 32 scenes, YOLACT++ distilled 543 unique IDs and 76340 images in total following the same procedure for detection association as in re-OBJ [2]. For training, we gather unique objects which appear at least 20 times through the scene. We then randomly select 8 images containing each unique ID to form the training dataset. Each triplet folder has 24 images for each object in a specific scene, which is comprised of 8 As, Ps, and Ns, respectively. After applying the criteria of the minimum number of appearances, 462 unique IDs and 13,005 images

per fg, bg, and full images are included in ReOBJ-Y++ for training, while the remaining part is employed as the test data. For the method evaluation, we take as probe all the images corresponding to 80 instance IDs from each dataset. The gallery images are the images captured from the same scene of the probe. Therefore, depending on the scene where the probe image is taken from, the set of gallery images can vary.

Finally, to perform a fair comparison with re-OBJ, we also used their dataset, named as ReOBJ-MR, where Mask R-CNN is used as ISB to split the fg and bg with a confidence score of 0.25. In ReOBJ-MR, there are 707 unique objects and 60,577 images selected from 27 scenes.

4.2 Ablation study

We conducted several experiments with different configurations of our method to justify our design choices throughout the pipeline. Besides, **re-OBJ**, in its original architecture, is trained and evaluated on each dataset to serve as a baseline. **Fast re-OBJ** uses both the fg and bg to form the embeddings that are further used to train the triplet network, as described in Section 3.2.

To examine the necessity of combining features from both fg and bg, we present **Fast re-OBJ** (fg) that only uses fg <https://www.overleaf.com/project/5e662d5299b03b00013c3e0b> feature to train the triplet network. To justify the use of bbx for splitting the ProtoNet output, rather than using the mask output, we present **Fast re-OBJ** (mask) that uses mask output from YOLACT++ prediction head for segmenting the ProtoNet output. Finally, to further investigate if adding more complete information to the embedding will result in a more discriminative embedding, we present **Fast re-OBJ** (full) that uses additionally full ProtoNet output together with the segmented fg and bg to form the final embedding via concatenation, resulting in a feature vector with a dimension of 6144. For **Fast re-OBJ** and its above-mentioned variants, we performed training separately on ReOBJ-Y++ and ReOBJ-GT, while testing only on the ReOBJ-Y++ to be realistic in real-world applications and to evaluate how inaccurate object detections affects Re-ID accuracy. **Fast re-OBJ** and its variants are not evaluated on ReOBJ-MR because **Fast re-OBJ** requires the ProtoNet outputs from YOLACT++ to form the embeddings.

Implementation details: The training lasted for 500 epochs, and we scheduled the learning rate to decrease exponentially with the margin for triplet loss set to

0.2. Adam [17] is used as the optimiser. We run our method on a standard PC with an i7-9750 CPU running at 2.60GHz and a GPU of Nvidia GTX 1080ti on Ubuntu 18.04 LTS.

Result discussion: Table 1 reports the dataset-specific mAP scores and time performance by **Fast re-OBJ** and its variants, as well as re-OBJ. We notice that **Fast re-OBJ** and its variants are considerably faster than re-OBJ in terms of the overall processing speed. The speed improvement is brought by both the ISB module by replacing Mask R-CNN with YOLACT++ and the EGM by generating embeddings directly from YOLACT++ outputs rather than extracting features with an additional ResNet model as in re-OBJ. Besides, TbM for each method shows similar speed performance where the slight variance is mainly due to the embedding size.

Moreover, compared to re-OBJ, **Fast re-OBJ** achieves higher Re-ID accuracy in terms of mAP by 3.4 when trained and tested on the ReOBJ-Y++ dataset, while improving the speed by 12 fps. When evaluated on the ReOBJ-GT dataset, **Fast re-OBJ** can improve over re-OBJ in terms of mAP by 2.94. The higher improvement of **Fast re-OBJ** over re-OBJ on the ReOBJ-Y++ dataset than the ReOBJ-GT dataset might be partially due to the bias that **Fast re-OBJ** exploits some part of YOLACT++ for the Re-ID task. By comparing **Fast re-OBJ** (fg) against **Fast re-OBJ**, we observe that using both bg and fg has a more discriminative embedding than only using fg for Re-ID task. When using additionally the full ProtoNet output, we notice that **Fast re-OBJ** (full) performs slightly better than **Fast re-OBJ** in Re-ID accuracy, however, its processing speed is slower due to additional processing in EGM and TbM. Finally, Re-ID accuracy achieved by **Fast re-OBJ** (mask) is similar to **re-OBJ** and worse than **Fast re-OBJ**. This justifies that using bbx for fg and bg segmentation is more robust for the Re-ID task compared to using instance masks, which also slows down the system by ~ 2.5 fps compared to **Fast re-OBJ**, where the main speed drop occurs in the EGM.

We do notice that the performance of our proposed method and its variants when trained with ReOBJ-GT dataset are lower than the ones trained with ReOBJ-Y++. This may suggest that training with perfect GT object detection does not enable the triplet network to be robust to imperfect real-world detection/segmentation outputs while training the network with imperfect segmentation is empirically better.

Table 1 Ablation study of variants of **Fast re-OBJ** on three datasets, ReObj-MR, ReObj-Y++, and ReObj-GT. Time performance is given for **ISB**, **EGM**, and **TbM** separately, and as a whole.

Method	mAP per dataset \uparrow			Speed [fps] \uparrow (Time [ms] \downarrow)			
	ReOBJ-MR	ReOBJ-GT	ReOBJ-Y++	ISB	EG	TbM	Total
re-OBJ	67.8	54.4	66.9	4.5 (222.22)	19.4 (51.55)	41.3 (24.21)	3.36 (297.62)
Fast re-OBJ (fg)	-	52.88	61.9	31.7 (31.55)	92.1 (10.86)	51.7 (19.34)	16.2 (61.73)
Fast re-OBJ (mask)	-	54.14	66.3	31.7 (31.55)	59.6 (16.78)	45.7 (21.88)	14.24 (70.22)
Fast re-OBJ (full)	-	58.07	70.9	31.7 (31.55)	72.4 (13.81)	30.1 (33.22)	12.73 (78.55)
Fast re-OBJ	-	57.34	70.3	31.7 (31.55)	85.5 (11.70)	45.7 (21.88)	15.36 (65.10)

Table 2 Comparison of the state-of-the-art methods on the three dataset, ReObj-MR, ReObj-Y++, and ReObj-GT, with the bg/fg split by Mask R-CNN, YOLACT++, and ground-truth, respectively.

Method	mAP per dataset \uparrow			Speed [fps] \uparrow (Time [ms] \downarrow)
	ReObj-MR	ReObj-GT	ReObj-Y++	
GEM	54.7	50.8	54.1	1.7 (588.24)
GEM (AP)	55.9	52.4	54.5	1.03 (970.88)
R-ASMK	61.3	54.3	61.1	1.41 (709.22)
AGRL	61.4	54.2	62.1	1.28 (781.25)
OSNET	65.5	55.8	64.2	2.83 (353.36)
PERMATRACK	65.4	56.6	66.7	4.54 (220.26)
re-OBJ	67.8	54.4	66.9	3.36 (297.62)
Fast re-OBJ	-	57.34	70.3	15.36 (65.10)

4.3 Comparison with the state-of-the-art methods

We compare our proposed **Fast re-OBJ** with re-OBJ [2] for object Re-ID task, and a set of recent person/vehicle Re-ID methods including AGRL [43], PERMATRACK [39], and OSNET [47]. We also performed comparison against related state-of-the-art image retrieval methods, i.e. GEM [28], GEM(AP) [31], and R-ASMK [38]. GEM enhances the training data with reconstructions and reports to obtain state-of-the-art results on image retrieval. GEM(AP) is built on top of GEM and claims accuracy improvement due to the use of a list-wise ranking loss with a multi-staged optimisation setup during training. Finally, R-ASMK uses a two-staged regional aggregation method, which first extracts local features and then combines the features to selectively match filters.

Table 2 reports the Re-ID accuracy as mAP and the time performance of our methods and the compared methods tested on the three datasets. Note that the object Re-ID methods are developed under the objective of searching for the match of the exact object instance, while the image retrieval methods are developed for searching similar objects amongst the gallery images. Therefore, the image retrieval methods are outperformed by the object Re-ID methods when being evaluated under more rigorous criterion, i.e. the Re-ID accuracy. Moreover, image retrieval methods are slower than our proposed methods due to their more complicated architecture. The Re-ID based models such as AGRL, OSNet, and PERMATRACK were originally developed for person and/or vehicle Re-ID purposes. For fair comparison, we retrained their feature extractors through the given loss functions in the original works to pro-

duce results on our newly generated dataset containing objects rather than pedestrians and vehicles. Due to its pose-specific and feature affinity based setup that also relies on temporal resolutions, AGRL appears to be disadvantageous like instance retrieval based methods for re-id of different objects than person. In contrast, OSNet and PERMATRACK achieve acceptable performances especially when ReObj-GT dataset is used. However, even re-OBJ achieves better results when ReObj-MR or ReObj-Y++ is employed as the dataset. Eventually, **Fast re-OBJ** surpasses all other methods regarding both accuracy and speed when tested on all three datasets.

In addition, we report CMC curves of different methods evaluated on three datasets in Fig. 5. CMC serves as one of the standard metrics for evaluating the accuracy of Re-ID methods vs. rank. We compare the predicted outputs with the queried object and compute a ranked list according to the probabilities. We consider the top-N accuracy, i.e. to check if the exact queried instance is contained or not in the top-N ranked gallery images.

On ReOBJ-MR dataset, **re-OBJ** shows remarkably better performance than other image retrieval methods but not that much better than person/vehicle Re-ID based methods, namely AGRL, OSNet, and PERMATRACK, where they become almost the same after Rank-10. On ReOBJ-Y++ dataset, the distinction between methods for object Re-ID and image retrieval remains considerable, while our **Fast re-OBJ** and **Fast re-OBJ (full)** outperform all other methods in terms of accuracy especially between Rank-2 and Rank-10. All compared methods saturate significantly after Rank-20 for each dataset. The steepness of the slope decreases notably after Rank-5 for each method.

Finally, we show in Fig. 6 some retrieved images within the top-4 rank with our method and its variants, by comparing the probe image with all the gallery images. The first row shows the resulted ranked images when querying an image of *backpack* with **Fast re-OBJ (mask)**, where the first two predictions were incorrect and the correct match is ranked as the 3rd. The second row queries for a *trash can* with our proposed **Fast re-OBJ**, where the first two predictions are correctly corresponding to the same *trash can*. The

Fig. 5 The CMC curves of our methods and the-state-of-art methods tested on the three datasets, ReOBJ-MR, ReOBJ-Y++, and ReOBJ-GT, respectively (best viewed in color).

final row demonstrates the query of *couch* with **Fast re-Obj (full)**, which yields the correct output in the first rank even it is partially visible from a very different viewpoint. Moreover, the consecutive predictions also look-alike to the A image.

5 Conclusions

We proposed an efficient framework, **Fast re-Obj**, to address the task of real-time object Re-ID in rigid scenes. Our proposed framework is tightly coupled with YOLACT++ whose instance segmentation backbone is used not only for object detection but also for generating more distinctive instance embeddings for triplet-based training. Moreover, we generated a couple of datasets with both ground-truth and YOLACT++ detections to benchmark the object Re-ID performance with the presence of imperfect detections. With extensive experiments, we justified our design choices in

Fig. 6 Qualitative result of Rank-N predictions achieved by variants of **Fast re-Obj** for querying *backpack* at the 1st row, *trash can* at the second row, and *couch* at the third row. The top-1 prediction obtained by **Fast re-Obj (mask)** in the first row is wrong as it contains a different instance from the one in the probe image, while the correct prediction is ranked the third among the gallery images. On the other hand, the top-2 predictions of **Fast re-Obj** that are presented at the second row are all correct as they contain the exact instance of the probe image, whilst in the third row, the top-1 prediction of **Fast re-Obj (full)** is correct even when there exist many similar instances among the gallery images.

terms of embedding generation and proved that our proposed framework can run in real-time at 15Hz on a standard PC with improved Re-ID accuracy in challenging scenes compared to the state-of-the-art methods. As future work, we plan to integrate the **Fast re-Obj** into a real-time object-centric SLAM framework, which can be ultimately run on embedded systems.

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